

Analysis of the Determinants of Financial Performance in SMEs in Burkina Faso

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Abstract

The question of the financial performance of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) has been the subject of a number of studies, each with its own particular contribution to understanding the concept. The aim of this article is to analyze the determinants of the financial performance of Burkinabe SMEs. Specifically, it examines certain SME financial indicators to highlight those that have an influence on their financial performance. To this end, a number of profitability and financial structure ratios served as the study's basic variables. The study was carried out on a sample of sixty-one (61) SMEs. Statistical tests enabled us to obtain results. These results show a positive influence of elements such as economic profitability, commercial profitability and financial autonomy on the financial performance of SMEs. A better combination of these different elements increases the chances of SMEs being financially successful.

Key words: SME, Economic profitability, Commercial profitability, Financial autonomy, Financial performance.

1. Introduction and background

Value creation, as always, is one of the top priorities of today's business leaders. Sales, market share and even annual net profit are the yardsticks for determining whether a company has

succeeded in creating, or is capable of creating, wealth over a given timeframe, in line with the resources invested.

Burkina Faso's small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) are no exception to this rule of business life. Accounting for over 80% of the country's businesses, according to the NERE database, SMEs are rightly regarded as the backbone of the Burkinabe economy. This position is due in part to the importance of their participation in the production of national wealth, and in part to their contribution to job creation. According to the Chamber of Commerce and Industry (CCI-BF), SMEs make up the bulk of the country's private sector, contributing 35% to 40% of GDP. They are also responsible for the creation of over ninety thousand permanent direct jobs and tens of thousands of indirect jobs.

However, like all other businesses, Burkina Faso's SMEs are faced with the many challenges of market globalization and a turbulent economic and social environment (particularly in terms of security), all of which put their performance to the test. They need to boost their competitiveness on local, regional and international markets alike. Such competitiveness cannot be achieved without a financial base that enables them to generate momentum in all areas of corporate life.

This new global economic order imposes constraints on businesses in general, and on Burkina Faso's SMEs in particular, which they can only overcome if they generate sufficient earnings to absorb the costs of remunerating invested capital. It goes without saying that SMEs are highly dependent on the optimal management of their resources. It can only be viable if its resources are well managed. To ensure that the company's activities are profitable for all its stakeholders, profitability is of paramount importance. The profitability mission assigned to SMEs raises the issue of financial performance in economic terms. Mastery of the factors influencing SME financial performance can only be assimilated through an in-depth understanding and knowledge of these factors. One of the key issues when it comes to financial performance is determining a set of determinants from which it will be possible to raise the company to a desired level of performance.

This type of problem raises the issue of monitoring the financial performance of SMEs, and the need to make this performance an object of study in order to contribute to management decision-

making. It therefore seemed legitimate to analyze SME performance in terms of financial profitability (Meschi, 1998). This research aims to analyze the factors that determine the financial performance of SMEs in Burkina Faso. Its interest lies in its theoretical contribution to a better understanding of the specificity of SME financial performance management in a context where knowledge on the subject often remains partial. It also provides SME managers with a better understanding of the management realities of their companies. Our aim in this article is to answer the following research question: what are the determinants of financial performance in SMEs in Burkina Faso, and what analysis can be made of them? To answer this central question, we put forward the following three hypotheses: (1) the financial performance of SMEs improves when they have a good level of economic profitability; (2) the financial performance of SMEs increases when they have an acceptable level of commercial profitability; (3) the more financially autonomous SMEs are, the better they perform financially.

In view of the above, this article is structured around five points. After this introduction and contextualization (1), four further points are devoted to a review of the literature on financial performance (2), a presentation of the research methodology and data used (3), a presentation of the results and their discussion (4) and finally the conclusion of the article (5).

2. Literature review on financial performance

The notion of performance is said to come ethymologically from the Latin verb "performare", which in the 13th century became the Old French "parformer" and "parfourmer" (Pradier, 2013), meaning "to accomplish" or "to execute" (Issor, 2017). The term was borrowed again from English during the 19th century to be applied in equestrian circles (1839), then among sportsmen (1872, 1876, 1877), among physiologists (1869), among engineers (1929) (Pradier, 2013) and subsequently in many other fields.

A number of researchers are unanimous in recognizing that performance is the result of an action. It is therefore the ex-post evaluation of the results obtained, without value judgment (Bouquin, 1986). In this vein, Bourguignon (2000) defines performance as the achievement of organizational objectives, whatever their nature and variety. Thus, the achievement of objectives is to be understood in the strict sense of an outcome, i.e. a result. A performance

could be a quantified result, an official statement indicating a result achieved with reference to an initial objective, whatever the field (Notat, 2007).

When it comes to business, the watchword these days is: "you have to perform in order to guarantee the survival and sustainability of your organization, and otherwise increase your competitive advantage..." (Issor, 2017). When asked about his market strategy, Charles de Croisset, Chairman of Crédit Commercial de France (CCF), after asserting that the market expects his company to perform well, concludes: "our objective is consistent with its own." (Albouy, 2006). For management theorists, these words, which reveal the full reality of corporate life, are not new. Indeed, the objective of any company is to maximize its value, to produce a return on invested capital. This objective has become a managerial reality in companies, to the point of imposing on managers the need to involve staff in the task of financial performance. As a result, managers are obliged to use tools or systems of varying degrees of precision and complexity to measure the financial performance of their companies (Tiona Wamba & Bekono, 2020).

Whatever the implications of the financial performance imperative, proponents of the concept assert that its achievement appears to be a common goal for all companies, as it is the principal means of corporate survival, and its measurement is an essential dimension (Amblard, 2007). Financial performance is generally assessed from financial statement data (Raymond & St-Pierre, 2005), based on the analysis of certain financial indicators linked to the company's activity and financial structure (Tiona Wamba & Bekono, 2020); these indicators make it possible to evaluate liquidity, solvency, return on investment, etc., in accordance with the rules of financial management, and make it possible to determine the company's financial viability (OM, 2014).

According to Sloan (1964), financial performance can be measured by means of indicators capable of measuring not only the economic return on capital (the ratio of net operating income to capital invested), but also the financial return on capital provided by owners (the ratio of net income to shareholders' equity). These two indicators can be combined with commercial profitability, obtained by dividing net income by sales excluding taxes (net income / sales

excluding taxes), and financial autonomy, calculated by dividing total shareholders' equity by total liabilities (shareholders' equity / total liabilities). Accounting as a measurement system provides a number of indicators, the best-known and most exposed of which is net income. Although the foundations, construction and capacity of this final balance to reflect a company's financial performance have been the subject of several scientific studies, these have not been able to shake its status (Amblard, 2007). This makes it the leading measure of corporate financial performance. In this vein, Issor (2017) considers that the financial approach to performance amounts to asking the following question: "How does the organization position itself in relation to its shareholders?" and answering it with an objective of profit maximization and return on investment. This means achieving the profitability that shareholders want, so as to perpetuate the company.

However, there are also those who criticize the purely financial side of the accounting model. In the early 1980s, in view of the turbulent and competitive business environment, a number of authors such as Gomes et al. (2004) argued against accounting models. Also, Kaplan and Norton (2001) and a number of authors with them, such as Kennerley and Neely (2003), went further, denouncing the limitations of accounting or financial measures in that they are historical, offer little indication of future performance, and fail to take into account the intangible elements of a company's value. Other authors also point to the fact that these measures are not linked to the strategy pursued by management (Saint Pierre et al, 2005), to effectiveness, efficiency, economy of resources, equity (Vogel, 2005), quality (Deming, 2002), and so on. Critics have also pointed out the arbitrary nature of this accounting model, which tends to privilege a single point of view, that of the company's owner: the shareholder (the shareholders' approach). Critics of the accounting model's net income, which makes it possible to assess the profitability or otherwise of the firm, contrast it with what they consider to be a fairer approach, that of stakeholders (Boisselier, 1991).

The main merit of the stakeholder approach would be to force managers to consider the company's key decisions within a much broader framework, taking into account not only the interests of shareholders, but also those of stakeholders (customers, creditors, suppliers, employees and public authorities) who are often the most active in the life of the firm (Bingo, 2016). Stakeholder theory sees the firm as a formula for creating shared value. A pluralistic

vision that puts the firm's rent as a quest for all of an organization's stakeholders (Ait El Amria & Attouch, 2016). Freeman (1984) defines stakeholders as any group or individual who may affect or be affected by the achievement of the firm's objectives. From this perspective, the company's objective would no longer be to maximize accounting profit alone, but to achieve a global productivity surplus that can be shared as widely as possible.

Such a position, which aims to rebalance the divergent interests of all company players, is up against a major adversary, the shareholders' approach, mentioned above, which seems to have the upper hand. The influence of net income is such that many major decisions (hiring, redundancies, investments, abandonment of activity, restructuring, etc.) depend on its actual or expected amount. In fact, the feverishness of market operators and the fluctuations in stock prices that follow earnings announcements bear witness to the importance attached to it (Amblard, 2007). In view of this, the logic of the accounting model seems to us to be acceptable for this study. This accounting model calls for the analysis of several financial ratios (Ooghe et al., 2000), leading to the deduction of a viable or non-viable situation for the companies studied.

3. Research methodology and data used

To analyze the financial performance of Burkinabè SMEs, we used data obtained from a series of semi-structured interviews we conducted with sixty-one Burkinabè SMEs, respecting the anonymity of the entities concerned. The sixty-one SMEs surveyed are classified according to the different sectors of economic activity, as shown in the table below.

Table 1: Breakdown of SMEs by business sector

Sector of activity	Number	Proportion (%)
Agriculture	18	29,5
Industry	17	27,87
Service	26	42,63
TOTAL	61	100

Source: Author's calculations (Eviews 10)

For the purposes of analysis, we took as variables financial ratios that are already familiar in financial analysis. For example, we used ROE (Return On Equity), which stands for return on equity. It's a financial ratio that enables us to assess a company's financial profitability over time. We also took into account three other ratios linked to the study's hypotheses: the economic profitability ratio, the commercial profitability ratio and the financial autonomy ratio, which are associated with the notion of profitability. The table below summarizes the ratios considered and how they are expressed.

Table 2: Ratios and their expressions

	Ratio	Expression
Financial performance	Return On Equity (ROE)	Net income/Equity
Economic profitability	Economic profitability ratio	Operating income/Invested capital
Commercial profitability	Commercial profitability ratio	Net income / Sales (excl. VAT)
Financial autonomy	Financial autonomy ratio	Shareholders' equity/Total liabilities

Source: Author's calculations (Eviews 10)

The higher the ROE, the more profitable the capital used by the company. If this ratio increases from year to year, or remains at a high level, this reflects good financial performance for SMEs. The three specific hypotheses suggest that the economic profitability ratio, the commercial profitability ratio and the financial autonomy ratio have a positive influence on the financial performance of SMEs. These three hypotheses will only be confirmed on condition of a positive correlation between ROE and the other ratios, on the one hand, and an existing influence of the latter on ROE, on the other. This condition is studied using appropriate statistical tests, in this case the correlation test and the Granger causality test, with a confidence threshold of 5%.

The interpretation techniques used are essentially descriptive. Borrowed from statistics, descriptive techniques enable us to arrive at a simplified representation of more complex realities. According to the French Scientific Evaluation Board, statistics can be defined as "the set of mathematical interpretation techniques applied to phenomena for which an exhaustive study of all factors is impossible due to their large number and complexity" (CSE, 1993). Descriptive techniques enable not only a synthetic presentation of the information contained in a set of data, but also the revelation of the logic that prevails in this set. The information gathered is processed using two software programs. Firstly, we used the 2016 version of Excel to calculate the various ratios used as variables in the study. Secondly, we used version 10 of Eviews, which has the advantage of offering a number of features for handling data for statistical analysis.

3. Results and discussion

The main statistical characteristics of the study database, including mean, minimum, maximum and median values and standard deviations, are presented in the following table:

Table 3: Descriptive statistics

	Financial Performance	Financial Autonomy	Commercial Profitability	Economic Profitability
Average	0, 02345	0, 3047	0, 29234	0, 02733
Median	0, 02910	0, 08255	0, 02495	0, 01547
Maximum	0,86437	0, 77121	0,65289	0, 89676
Minimum	-0,18004	0, 00429	-0,05169	-0, 17823
Standard deviation	0, 16663	0, 19108	0, 14979	0, 16158

Source: Author's calculations (Eviews 10)

On average, SMEs have a financial performance (Net Income/Equity) equal to 0.02345 and a commercial profitability (Net Income/Sales (excl. VAT)) equal to 0.29234. Average sales profitability is significantly higher than average financial performance. Sales are more important than equity. The average of financial autonomy and economic profitability are also positive, but the value of the average remains very low.

Also, 50% of SMEs have a financial performance below 0.02910, financial autonomy below 0.08255, commercial profitability below 0.02495 and economic profitability below 0.01547. In contrast, 50% of SMEs have financial performance, financial autonomy, commercial profitability and economic profitability above each of the corresponding median values.

Furthermore, the dispersion around the mean is 0.16663 for financial performance, 0.19108 for financial autonomy, 0.14979 for commercial profitability and 0.16158 for economic profitability.

These descriptive statistics allow us to go further in the study by means of a correlation test, which gives us the possibility of assessing the dependency between variables. The various dependencies observed between financial performance, financial autonomy, commercial profitability and economic profitability are reported in the table below:

Table 4: Correlation test results

	Financial Performance	Financial Autonomy	Commercial Profitability	Economic Profitability
Financial Performance	1.000000	0.016344	0.079424	0.065060
Financial Autonomy	0.066344	1.000000	-0.003851	0.144396
Commercial Profitability	0.079424	-0.003851	1.000000	0.271458
Economic Profitability	0.025060	0.144396	0.271458	1.000000

Source: Author's calculations (Eviews 10)

The results of the correlation test show a positive relationship between financial performance and each of the other variables: financial autonomy, commercial profitability and economic profitability. The values of these relationships are 0.066344, 0.079424 and 0.025060

respectively. The presence of this relationship enables us to carry out a Granger causality test. In Granger's sense, one variable causes another if the causal variable improves the prediction of the caused variable. The Granger causality test yields the results shown in the following table:

Table 5: Granger causality test results

	Obs	F-Statistic	Prob.
Financial autonomy - Financial performance	122	0.95077	0.04923
Financial performance - Financial autonomy	122	0.97594	0.03506
Commercial profitability - Financial performance	122	0.96081	0.04361
Financial performance - Commercial profitability	122	0.22837	0.78563
Economic profitability - Financial performance	122	0.97014	0.04986
Financial performance - Economic profitability	122	0.04824	0.97176

Source: Author's calculations (Eviews 10)

As shown in the table above, the causality test between financial performance and the other three variables, namely financial autonomy, commercial profitability and economic profitability, leads to the following observations:

- the existence of causality between the three variables (financial autonomy, commercial profitability, economic profitability) and financial performance;
- the existence of causality from financial performance to financial autonomy;
- the existence of non-causality from financial performance to commercial profitability and economic profitability.

The results can be discussed in relation to the study's three hypotheses. In concrete terms, this involves comparing the results obtained for each hypothesis to assess whether or not they are acceptable, and then analyzing them.

The first hypothesis suggests that economic profitability is an explanatory factor in the financial performance of SMEs. The result of the correlation test between economic profitability and financial performance showed a positive value of 0.025060; a value which, despite being positive, remains low (it is less than 0.5). Furthermore, beyond the weakness of this relationship, the causality test reveals a causal link between economic profitability and financial performance with a P-value of 4.98%. Compared with the significance threshold, this P-value is below the 5% level. The first hypothesis is confirmed.

The second hypothesis suggests that commercial profitability has a positive influence on the financial performance of Burkinabe SMEs. The correlation test showed a positive relationship between commercial profitability and financial performance, with a value of 0.079424. Commercial profitability and financial performance therefore move in the same direction. This relationship, albeit weak, is confirmed by the causality test, which shows a unidirectional causality from sales profitability to financial performance, with a P-value of 4.36%. This P-value is below the confidence threshold (5%): the second hypothesis is accepted.

The third hypothesis suggests that the financial affluence of Burkinabe SMEs has an influence on their level of financial performance. The results of the correlation and causality tests support this hypothesis. Indeed, the value of the correlation between financial autonomy and financial performance is positive, with a value of 0.066344. This value, like that of economic profitability and commercial profitability, remains low. However, the causality test reveals a causal link between financial autonomy and financial performance. This causal link indicates a P-value of 4.92%. Compared with the significance threshold, this is below the 5% level. The third hypothesis is confirmed. Financial autonomy is an explanatory factor for financial performance. Similar results have already been found. Pinteris in 2002 and Kabwigiri and Hakizimana in 2014, in their studies of the banking sector in Argentina and Burundi respectively, came to the conclusion that capital concentration has a positive effect on financial performance in the banking sector.

The various results confirm our hypotheses, but it has to be said that the P-value values are slightly below the accepted risk rate of 5%. The influence of economic profitability, commercial profitability and financial autonomy on financial performance remains fragile. This fragility is

explained by difficulties specific to SMEs, notably in terms of access to financial resources, access to administrative services, and so on. Indeed, the results of the EESE (Enabling environment for sustainable enterprises) survey show that in Burkina Faso, out of every hundred businesses that apply for credit, only thirty obtain it. And of those that do, over 69.2% find it difficult to obtain the loan (ILO, 2017). This testifies to the difficulty SMEs have in mobilizing external resources. Most of them are often forced to mobilize personal savings (own funds, retained profits) or consume resources generated during the operating cycle. On top of this, it should be noted that credit is offered at a cost that is deemed prohibitive, and within a timeframe that is quite long for companies. The time it takes from the preparation and submission of applications to the release of funds can be as long as several months, which limits SMEs' ability to compete and contributes to their inability to meet their financial obligations. As a result, the financial structure of SMEs is affected, leading them to critical levels of solvency (Cultrera, 2016).

SME financing is also hampered by the absence of a credit culture, and the lack of collateral or risk prevention mechanisms among SMEs prevents them from gaining easy access to competitively priced credit. For example, in the EESE study, over 44.55% of companies were unable to obtain credit due to insufficient collateral. Administrative obstacles also hinder SME performance. Despite the many reforms and transparency mechanisms put in place by the public authorities, the malfunctioning of certain public administration departments and the lack of transparency in administrative procedures are obstacles encountered by SMEs. Symptoms of dysfunctional administrative services include rising absenteeism among public servants, declining quality of service, and slowness to adapt to change and anticipate (ESF, 2009). The phenomenon of lack of transparency can be seen in the divergent interpretations of administrative procedures; interpretations that are sometimes subjective or even abusive on the part of administrative agents, prompting entrepreneurs and SMEs in particular to assert their demand for service by covert means, or to pursue their activities on the bangs of legal norms and procedures. The ESF survey shows that, for the majority of companies, contract award processes are still not transparent enough, and are a breeding ground for corruption and influence peddling (ESF, 2009). This way of operating means that SMEs are not in a position

to respond to calls for tender or to supply goods or services to customers in complete transparency.

These various obstacles create a considerable gap between the actual performance of SMEs and their potential performance. The purpose of the economic profitability ratio is to translate the profit achieved before extraordinary items and tax for each franc invested in the company. The low value of this ratio in this study raises the question of the economic efficiency of SMEs. Many SMEs are faced with problems of optimizing the resources they commit to the operating cycle. This can be explained by factors such as poor management of economic capital (fixed assets and working capital requirements).

In addition to the question of optimizing invested resources, there is also the question of commercial optimization. Traditionally, sales profitability is used to estimate the impact of sales on earnings. Good sales profitability reflects the company's ability to win market share, and therefore sales, and therefore profits, if other management factors are kept under control. In this study, even if the issue of commercial optimization is not as pronounced as that of resource optimization, the fact remains that over 47% of companies have a commercial profitability below 20%. This may be explained by the exposure of Burkinabe SMEs to competition and the security situation. Competition is all the more fierce as most Burkinabe SMEs, if they are to survive, must make their products more competitive (quality, price) in the image of products from China or elsewhere.

In addition, financial independence remains a key concern for a large number of Burkinabe SMEs. Indeed, more than half of SMEs have a financial independence ratio of 0.20 or less. In contrast, barely 20% of SMEs have a financial independence ratio of over 0.60. Overall, the solvency of SMEs is at stake here. This solvency is vital, as an insolvent SME runs the risk of bankruptcy. However, an SME that files for bankruptcy does not disappear on its own, but with jobs. This situation depends on the probable instability of the SME's financial structure, linked to financing problems. The problem of the financial autonomy of SMEs raises the question of their financing mechanisms.

The various problems raised require answers, hence the interest of a number of recommendations for SMEs and SME support structures. To improve their financial

performance, SMEs need to work towards better control of their economic and commercial risks, set up systems for monitoring and seeking financing, and make sure they choose the right financial structure. Because of their activities, SMEs run economic and commercial risks such as the misuse of available resources and the loss of market share due to competition. It is therefore desirable for every SME to take control of these risks by setting up alert mechanisms capable of drawing management's attention to major risks. These alerts can be used by managers to find appropriate solutions to achieve the economic and commercial objectives that are essential to boost financial performance. Monitoring is also a key driver of performance. With this in mind, it would be a good idea for every SME to set up a business intelligence and financing research system. Its role will be to draw up a financing strategy, identify financing opportunities and prepare the necessary steps to seize these opportunities. The choice of financial structure also depends on a number of parameters: the economic climate, the real interest rate, the growth of the sector's activity, the financial structure of competitors, etc. When choosing a structure, it is important for SMEs to take all these parameters into account, and to run simulations according to whether they wish to take on debt or equity financing; the consequences of the leverage obtained from each simulation could lead to an informed choice of financial structure.

On the government side, it would be advisable to facilitate access to SME support services, and to promote the use of financial experts as part of SME support. To boost their financial performance, SMEs need access to a range of financial and non-financial services. Access to financial services is a major constraint. It is therefore essential that the government of Burkina Faso step up its efforts to reduce this constraint, which undermines SME performance. To this end, it should lobby banks, financial institutions (FIs) and microfinance institutions (MFIs) to become more involved in SME financing. This lobbying work could focus on lowering interest rates, access to overdrafts, reducing the collateral required by credit institutions, etc. Non-financial services also help to improve SME performance. In this respect, it is important for the Burkina Faso government to use a number of levers that fall within the scope of these services. These include improving the transmission of market and price information, ensuring effective training and capacity-building for SME managers, promoting access to the technological process, developing beneficial partnerships with SMEs, and further streamlining administrative

procedures in favor of SMEs. In addition, as part of the support provided to SMEs, it would be advisable for public policies to make it compulsory for SMEs to use financial experts. The financial expert would be able to advise the SME manager, reminding him or her of the rules of good management, helping him or her to identify the viability of the business plan more quickly, ensuring the efficiency and quality of management and financial structuring, and proposing solutions to any difficulties encountered. The use of such experts could be made compulsory by the legislator, on condition that their remuneration is also set by the latter, taking into account the capacity of the less well-off SME. In this respect, the Maison de l'Entreprise du Burkina Faso (MEBF) could play a role by setting up a directory of accredited experts available to support SMEs according to the conditions set by the legislator.

4. Conclusion

Today, SMEs are at the heart of Burkina Faso's economic and social development strategy. Their role is to sustain the country's economic growth, but this cannot be achieved if the SMEs themselves are not performing well. The overall aim of the research was to analyze the factors that determine the financial performance of SMEs in Burkina Faso. Using the methods and tools deployed, we came to the conclusion that economic profitability, commercial profitability and financial autonomy are explanatory factors in the financial performance of Burkina Faso SMEs. Beyond this conclusion, we have to admit that the influence of these different variables on financial performance is weakened by difficulties such as problems of economic and commercial optimization and the concern for financial independence.

To remedy these shortcomings, we have identified a number of avenues and tools that concern both SMEs and the economic players who support them. For example, it is important for SMEs to work towards better control of their economic and commercial risks, to set up systems for monitoring and seeking financing, and to ensure that they choose the right financial structure. The State will also facilitate access to support services for SMEs and promote the use of financial experts in the context of SME support.

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